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Report from site visit

Assessor name	Milan Zdravković
University/organization	University of Gdansk
Assessor's bio (link)	https://www.linkedin.com/in/milanzdravkovic/
Evaluated scientific disciplines	Earth and related environmental sciences Economics and finance Management and quality studies Social and economic geography and spatial management Political science and public administration

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1.	<p style="text-align: center;">Evaluation of the planned actions in the field of academic assessment (e.g. consistency with the development strategy, involvement of authorities, participation of researchers in the creation of assessment rules) - max. 2000 characters</p> <p>Organization is strongly dependent on the government funding which is bound to the number of students and grade, which correspond mostly to the scientific performance as defined by the organizational assessment process, described in the national law. Researchers are assessed solely by the organization, which is using its own rules and indicators.</p> <p>There exists a high complementarity of national legislation and organizational rules related to organizational and individual assessment of researchers, respectively. This is perceived by the researchers as an issue, given that researchers are now obliged to fulfil all criteria in both of the evaluations, including funding performance and social impact, as required by the national legislation (organizational assessment) and teaching and administrative criteria, as required by the internal rules for individual assessment, while scientific performance was assessed in both cases.</p> <p>Rules for scientific performance assessment differ in cases of organizational and individual assessment. Organizational assessment is done based on the list of journals (and some conferences in IT) predefined by the national bodies, while individual assessment considers journals indexed by WoS/Scopus. Given the surprising misalignment of national list and IF-based ranking, such difference creates stress and pressure among researchers, related to not having a freedom to publish in what is considered by them the best opportunities. For example, management urges for publishing in journals with highest number of points according to the national list, while researchers want to publish in good journals, sometimes with high impact but with lower ranking at the list or even in journals edited by the reputable scientists, etc.</p> <p>According to some of the researchers, some discussions related to introducing the rules for individual assessment has been invited by the rectorate. However, it appears that no recommendations provided by them were considered.</p>
2.	<p style="text-align: center;">Consistency between assessed scientific achievements and results of scientific research in the evaluated disciplines - max. 2000 characters</p> <p>Rules for scientific performance assessment of the individual researchers, as defined by the organizational bylaw are different for the different scientific fields. Even though they are referring to a very simplistic quantitative indicators, they seem to be defined for each scientific field in the reasonable way.</p> <p>The individual assessment process and respective criteria do not take into account the specific aspect of funding required to do the research and report it in the scientific publication. For example, for some scientific fields, research product requires significant investment (travel and stay to experimentation facilities), while in other cases, none (desk research, data analysis). Thus, the performance in such two scientific fields is not comparable.</p>

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3.	<p>Substantial preparation for evaluation of scientific achievements (e.g. knowledge of basic indicators and principles of evaluation) - max. 2000 characters</p> <p>It appears that all researchers are very well informed about the indicators and principles of evaluation, both in organizational and individual assessment, even the researchers at earliest career stages.</p> <p>However, evaluation of young researchers suffers from major weaknesses, related to: a) lack of readiness of early career researchers to perform high quality research and publish accordingly in the first years of their contract, b) lack of mechanism for normalizing the scientific performance indicators on the assessed period.</p> <p>Interviewed researchers are very eager in insisting on reducing the teaching obligations, so to create more time availability for doing research.</p>
4.	<p>The course of the evaluation process (complexity, multi-stage, level of automation of the process) - max. 2000 characters</p> <p>Individual assessment is done at the level of scientific field, by the committee appointed by the dean. There is no process of recruiting the assessors or their training.</p> <p>Organizational scientific performance assessment is done by using a list of journals defined by the government and respective points allocated to each of them, as a reference. The issue is that sometimes the number of points allocated to the journals is changing. Number of points allocated to the published manuscript is bound to the time of publishing not the time of submission, which is a big issue as the duration of the total review and publishing process is completely uncertain and, in some cases, exceptionally long.</p> <p>The manner of sharing the total number of points awarded to the article published in the specific journal among co-authors is simply terrible as it involves sharing the points between the subset of authors working in the same department, while the sharing is not done with co-authors belonging to external organization. Such practice penalizes cooperation of researchers within departments.</p> <p>Evaluation of scientific performance does not consider qualitative criteria. Organizational evaluation considers number of points, based on the national journal ranking, while individual assessment considers only number of papers, indexed in WoS/Scopus.</p> <p>Individual assessment of the scientific performance considers only quantitative indicators related to the number of papers.</p> <p>Organizational assessment recognizes only successful projects/grants.</p> <p>UG implemented and is running CRIS, among the first universities in Poland. All quantitative indicators related to both types of assessment and more are monitored there.</p>

Strengths of the process of evaluating scientific achievements

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- Knowledge base system facilitates real-time overview of scientific performance at individual and aggregate levels.
- The researchers are in general well informed about both individual and organizational assessment processes, including criteria, even those at the earliest career stage.
- The criteria for scientific performance assessment at the individual level recognize the differences in publication practices across different scientific disciplines.
- There are evaluation committees, elected at the university and faculty levels, in charge for implementation of the assessment processes.

Weaknesses in the process of evaluating scientific achievements

- Individual and organizational assessment processes are not sufficiently aligned, in terms of indicators or required criteria (in fact, with exception of scientific performance assessment, they are criteria are complementary). That puts a heavy burden on researchers and sometimes even create a conflict due to the different level of strictness with regard to evaluating scientific performance at organizational and individual levels.
- The engagement of research community in defining the individual evaluation process is insufficient.
- The criteria for scientific performance assessment at the individual level does not recognize complex criteria and indicators, including the common ones (for example, journal guest editing, book editing, mobility experience, number of submitted project proposals, PhD mentoring and supervision, assessment of PhD theses, assessment of habilitation, participation in committees, organizing conference, reports, studies and those specific to the particular discipline (for example, participation in public forums, media participation, impact to legislation, etc.).
- Scientific performance assessment at the individual level is not normalized across scientific fields, thus creating difficulties in comparing the individual performance at different career stages and scientific fields (see Recommendations).
- The application of scientific performance assessment indicators at the individual level of early-career stage researchers over-penalizes their lack of skills and experiences normally occurring at the beginnings of their careers.
- The process of selection of members of evaluation committees is not transparent.

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Recommendations:

	High urgency	Low urgency
High importance	<p>When evaluating individual researchers, consider normalizing on the spent budget or funding weights, to favorize research that is normally done with lots of required funding and penalize the one that requires none, and so establish a comparability.</p> <p>Reconsider the individual assessment to better align the required outcomes with the outcomes required by the organizational assessment.</p> <p>For individual assessment, consider introducing other criteria common or those strictly specific to the specific scientific fields, for example, journal guest editing, book editing, mobility experience, number of submitted project proposals, PhD mentoring and supervision, assessment of PhD theses, assessment of habilitation, participation in committees, public forums, organizing conference, reports, studies, media participation, impact to legislation (through participation in law creation process, advisory roles, etc.) etc.</p> <p>Introduce a “grace” period of one year for early-stage researchers to compensate for lack of their skills for performing research work and writing papers at the beginning of their careers OR introduce peer-reviewed preliminary reports, datasets and other intermediary research results.</p> <p>Mentorship processes should be improved to facilitate empowering PhDs with knowledge and skills to publish, fund raising, etc. Introduce trainings for mentors/supervisors or co-mentorship practices.</p>	<p>Facilitate partial qualitative evaluation of the research work: consider adding new fields in the form for the submission of scientific publication in the for adding the comments on: 1) description of the contribution of the given co-author in the uploaded paper, 2) description of the alignment with the scientific field of the given co-author, 3) description of the alignment with the previous work, ongoing project, or existing university research strategy.</p>

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Low importance	<p>Setup a venue for continuous discussion of the researchers about the research assessment system and collection of proposals for their improvement. Strengthen the role of faculties by moving the budget for scientific publishing from university to faculty level.</p>	<p>Implement a training for the members of the evaluation committees. Introduce a process for recruitment of the evaluation committee members and competitive calls. Consider the rewards for such participation.</p>
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